

Supporting Information for

Assessment of groundwater well vulnerability to contamination through physics-informed machine learning

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Tutorial for calculating idups with the Calc_idups.py python script

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Tutorial for calculating idups with the Calc_idups.py python script

Files included:

- elev.tif – the digital elevation model; raster
- gw_10wells.shp – locations of 10 groundwater wells; point shapefile
- uogd_2wpd.shp – locations of 2 unconventional oil and gas development well pads; point shapefile

Notes:

1. These three files are projected to the same Spatial Reference.
2. **All three files must be in the same folder to avoid errors.**

Software used:

- ArcMap 10.7 with Spatial Analyst extension and Python interpreter (also tested with ArcMap 10.8 and ArcGIS Pro 2.7)
- TauDEM 5 (Tarboton, 2015)
- Notepad++

Overview:

The workflow used for calculating idups, or inverse distance to nearest upgradient UD source, in ArcMap is as follows:

- UD well locations (PADEP, 2020) were first converted to a raster file with 1 indicating presence and 0 indicating absence ("source" raster).
- TauDEM was used to process the digital elevation model with the following steps: 1. Pit Remove (generated the "fel" raster), 2. D-Infinity Flow Direction (generated the "ang" and "slp" rasters), 3. D-Infinity Avalanche Runout (generated the "dfs" and "rz" rasters), using the previously created UD source raster. The "Input alpha angle threshold" setting was set to a value of 0 so that the flow lines continued up to the lowest point in the DEM. Other settings were left at their default values. The dfs (distance from source) raster was then converted to a point shape file.
- Next, the Path Distance and Path Distance Allocation from Spatial Analyst were used to match each cell in the DEM to a dfs point, using the DEM as the Input Surface Raster. The maximum path distance was set to a default value of 500 m, such that distances exceeding this threshold were not allocated a dfs point and were thus considered to not be located downgradient of a UD source. idups was calculated as $1/(dfs+path_distance)$, and a value of 0 (i.e., an infinite denominator) was assigned to locations beyond the threshold path distance. This threshold path distance may be considered to account for the uncertainty in subsurface flow paths compared to surface flow paths, or it may be defined based on arguments from seasonal changes in flow direction or pumping-induced stream capture (Barlow & Leake, 2012). idups can be calculated using different values for the threshold path distance.

Step-by-step tutorial:

1. Open the Calc_idups.py script in Notepad++ (or your preferred text editor). The first block of code (Lines 17 to 30) contains three parameters that can be modified by simply changing the value in the text editor.

```
12
13 #####
14 # Adjustable parameters: Modify as needed
15 #####
16
17 ► bufferdist = "100 Meters"
23 ◀
24 ► expression = "getid2ups( !PathDist!, !grid code!, 500)"
28 ◀
29 ► inputProc= '4'
31 ◀
```

bufferdist – Buffer distance around each source location. Used in L73 of the code. Units must be specified by the user. If the source is considered as the well pad centroid, the buffer zone translates to the well pad area. A 100 meter buffer radius translates to about 3 hectares. Johnson et al. (2010) report that direct land disturbances from UD can range from 1.2 to 3.6 hectares, and can reach up to 12 hectares if indirect land disturbances are included. Meanwhile, Slonecker and Milheim (2015) report an average footprint of 2.5 hectares per unconventional drilling site.

expression –The expression used for calculating idups, with 500 set as the maximum path distance from surface flow paths to groundwater receptors. Used in L218 of the code. The user can change the value 500 as needed. Units will match the linear units used in the Spatial Reference. Receptors located beyond this threshold will not be considered downgradient of a source (i.e., assigned a distance to upgradient source of infinity, such that $idups = 1/infinity = 0$). Calculating idups using different values for the threshold path distance can also be done directly within the ArcGIS Field Calculator without modifying the script as shown below.

inputProc –This is the number of processes to be used by mpiexec. Must be an integer. Must not exceed the number of available cores*cpus for efficiency. 4 is usually an adequate choice for most desktop PC’s. Used in L104, 128, and 162 of the code.

2. Launch ArcMap. Go to Arc Toolbox. Right-click on an empty space in the panel and click

the Add Toolbox . (If you have not yet created a toolbox to add, see: <https://desktop.arcgis.com/en/arcmap/10.7/analyze/managing-tools-and-toolboxes/creating-a-custom-toolbox.htm>). Here we will assume that the toolbox is called MyToolbox.tbx

3. Right-click on MyToolbox then go to Add > Script. The Add Script dialog box will appear. Set the Name as idups and Label as Calc_idups. You can keep the other options to their

defaults. Click Next. For the Script file , navigate to the Calc_idups.py script.

4. Click Next. Now, we will define the inputs for the tool, following the same order that they appear on the script. We’ll name the input as follows:

Display Name	Data Type
Input source locations	Feature Layer
Input receptor locations	Feature Layer
DEM	Raster Layer

Note that Data Type is selected from a dropdown menu. Each parameter will have the following properties:

Parameter Properties	
Property	Value
Type	Required
Direction	Input
MultiValue	No
Default	
Environment	
Filter	None
Obtained from	
Symbology	

Click Finish.

5. We are now ready to run the tool. Add the three files – elev.tif, gw_10wells.shp, and uogd_2wpd.shp – to your map.
6. Double-click on the Calc_idups tool that you just created, and select the corresponding inputs:

- The script will run and create several files. You can add the created “dfs” raster to the map to see what the flow paths look like. **Note that the tool will give an error if these files already exist.** We recommend making renamed copies of the three original files if you want to rerun the tool, e.g., if you want to use a different value of “bufferdist”. idups will now appear as a new field in the attribute table of gw_10wells.shp

gw_10wells							
	FID	Shape	gw_well	PathDist	pointid	grid_code	idups
▶	0	Point	gw0	733.366	87	0	0
	1	Point	gw1	193.544	240	736.69	0.001075
	2	Point	gw2	30	96	319.706	0.00286
	3	Point	gw3	90.3321	286	1561.25	0.000605
	4	Point	gw4	121.088	330	2525.51	0.000378
	5	Point	gw5	115.119	291	1978.23	0.000478
	6	Point	gw6	134.315	352	3164.93	0.000303
	7	Point	gw7	242.278	362	3489.78	0.000268
	8	Point	gw8	243.324	367	3701.91	0.000253
	9	Point	gw9	1171.94	362	3489.78	0

Notice that Features 0 and 8 have idups = 0 because their PathDistance exceeds the maximum path distance used in the expression (set to 500 in the script). You do not need to rerun the script to test different values of the maximum path distance. You can simply Add Field to the attribute table, and use the Field Calculator with a Codeblock expression similar to L212-216 in the script.

For example, if we Add a new field idups_100 corresponding to a maximum path distance of 100, we can set:

Only Feature gw2 and gw3 will have a nonzero idups_100.

References

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Additional help

- Enabling the Spatial Analyst Extension - <https://desktop.arcgis.com/en/arcmap/latest/extensions/spatial-analyst/enabling-the-spatial-analyst-extension.htm>
- Executing tools within Python scripts in ArcGIS - <https://desktop.arcgis.com/en/arcmap/10.7/analyze/executing-tools/writing-python-scripts.htm>
- TauDEM 5 Troubleshooting - <https://hydrology.usu.edu/taudem/taudem5/support.html>